

THE EDUCATION OF UZBEK WOMEN IN THE 1920's AND 1930's: PROBLEMS IN THE FIELD

Mardieva Guzal Karimovna

Researcher of Samarkand State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12619933>

The time of the 1920s and 1930s in the XX century was the most contentious and intricate era in the cultural development of the Uzbek people. Following the October revolution in 1917 in Russia, the socio-political and economic transformations resulted in intricate and conflicting developments in cultural affairs. These intricate processes had a significant impact on the field of education, which held a crucial position in the cultural fabric of society. During the 20–30s, there were conflicting factors that influenced the study of historical problems. This text explores a combination of progressive advancements and tragic elements in its development. Specifically, it discusses the emergence of democratic development trends in culture, which were later replaced by extensive and controlled methods. It also highlights the significant increase in enthusiasm for education among the masses, alongside thoughtless reforms. Additionally, it mentions the formation of a new intellectual group and the elimination of older personnel, as well as the rise in literacy levels and the establishment of bureaucracy.

In the early 1920s, the Bolsheviks pursued a strategy of “cultural construction” with the primary objective of establishing “communist upbringing” in Turkestan. This involved removing “old things” from the brains of the people and replacing them with a “new culture”. Specifically, the implementation of policies aimed at enhancing women's literacy within the education system and empowering their participation in social activities has resulted in profound transformations in the lives of Uzbek women. These changes, which include the violation of moral and normative principles such as undermining Muslim traditions and national customs, have both liberated women from the direct and indirect oppression they face and yielded specific outcomes in addressing issues like female illiteracy and workforce development.

It is important to acknowledge that the educational reforms introduced in the early 1900s were the result of the endeavors of modernists. The topic of women has gained particular significance among the national progressives, particularly in the areas of religion, education, enlightenment, journalism, and literature, with a focus on reforming views. Abdulkadir Shakuri, an enthusiastic advocate for knowledge and education, was the pioneer in founding a progressive school for females in Samarkand during the early 1900s [G.Normurodova: 122–127].

Prior to 1917, the modernist press mostly emphasized the liberation of women in the public sphere. However, from the early 1920s, they began advocating for the inclusion of women in all aspects of society. This is demonstrated by the fact that, in the final decade of the Russian Empire, there was significant focus among intellectuals who advocated for reforms on the matter of gender [Paolo Sartori: 200–201].

Subsequently, the Jadids displayed significant enthusiasm for the education sector at Soviet educational institutions and actively encouraged women to pursue study in this arena. The courses for female teachers, established in 1919, were codified as the Teacher's Institute (School of Women and Girls) by a collaborative initiative of intellectual men and women. During the early 1920s, the “Land of Knowledge” was populated by a group of individuals who had completed their study and obtained degrees from teaching and pre-school educational institutions. Despite receiving financial support from Turkompros (Turkestan Education

Committee), the women's organization “Bilim Yurti” maintained its Jadidist character until the mid-1920s [Adeeb Khalid: 199–200].

Consequently, educated women began to emerge in the media and even on the theater stage. Subsequently, there were also women among the students who were transferred to Moscow and Germany. The Soviet authorities made significant efforts to encourage local women to attend schools and eliminate illiteracy. To recruit students to schools, a range of incentives were also offered. The Council of People's Commissars of the Turkestan ASSR made a decision on November 11, 1924. This decision granted preferential loans and privileges from agricultural banks to women who completed schools for the eradication of illiteracy, as well as to farmers who completed six-month courses. In the academic year 1924–1925, a total of 5010 individuals were registered for literacy courses in the Samarkand region. Among them, 322 were women and 155 were Uzbeks [D.Akramov: 19–20].

Nevertheless, it is important to acknowledge that the analysis of literacy rates is more intricate than the aforementioned figures imply. The location of students' residences was a significant determinant of literacy rates, given that the majority of early schools were situated in urban regions. In the 1920s, there was a notable growth in the number of state-operated primary schools catering to urban Uzbek girls. However, it was not until the 1930s that the number of rural schools started to rise. Consequently, this had a significant influence on literacy. Research indicates that in 1926, the literacy rate in urban parts of Uzbekistan was approximately 3.8 percent, however in rural areas, this figure was less than 1 percent. Due to the fact that the majority of the inhabitants resided in settled communities [Sevket Hylton Akyildiz: 8].

From 1917 to 1920, several government decisions and decrees were made that established the development of the educational system on a new foundation. In 1918, the Central Executive Committee of the Republic of Turkestan endorsed the regulation "On the Organization of Public Education of Turkestan". This regulation mandated the provision of free education in the native language to all students and the secularization of schools. In the 1920s, a concerted effort was made to eliminate illiteracy among the older population, following the enactment of this statute. In 1926, particular emphasis was placed on women with a literacy rate of less than three percent. Evening and “likbez” schools were created in Central Asia. In 1930, the Central Committee of the Communist Party of Uzbekistan approved the implementation of “On the Introduction of General Compulsory Education for Children and Adolescents”, which mandated that children must attend school during daylight hours [A.Elizabeth Constantine: 97].

Concurrently with education, women engaged in upbringing activities that aligned with the principles of “communist upbringing”. Considerable emphasis was placed on the development of distinct women's clubs in Turkestan. The inaugural Women's club was established in 1924 in the historic city of Tashkent. At first, a total of 250 ladies from the local area were drawn to this group. During the latter part of 1924, Women's clubs were founded in Samarkand, Kokand, Fergana, Margilon, and various other places [Uzbekiston tarixi: 337].

Co-education was implemented exclusively within the nomadic and semi-nomadic Kazakh and Kyrgyz communities, although even in these settings, the number of girls attending schools was far lower than that of boys. The enrollment of indigenous females in schools commenced during the academic year of 1923/24, facilitated by the registration of girls by the Turkestan People's Commissariat of Education. In the current year, there were a total of 1,786 females from the local population attending schools. Among them, 1,344 were Uzbek, 242 were Kazakh, 86 were Turkmen, 72 were Tajik, and 50 were Taman. Furthermore, the country is home to 1139

national minorities, including Tatars, Jews, Bashkirs, Persians, and others [J.Khasanbaev: 47].

During the academic year 1923/24, a total of fourteen women's schools were established in the Syrdarya region, twelve in the Fergana region, and four in Samarkand specifically for Uzbek girls. Ninety six women's schools were established in Uzbekistan by the 1924/25 academic year. There were a combined total of 23,308 students enrolled in both women's and mixed schools. Based on statistical data, it may be inferred that the figure of 442,673 girls of school age in 1926 is a noteworthy achievement, since it corresponds to a 9% increase in a relatively little timeframe [K.Nishonboyeva: 101].

Prior to the implementation of mandatory education, the enrollment of girls in schools was extremely limited. During the school enrollment period in the 1927/28 school year, there were a total of 133,400 students, out of which 34,700 were enrolled. This implies that it is equivalent to 26 percent. A total of 6,000 female students were enrolled in rural schools, accounting for 11.5 percent of the overall student population. In the 1938/39 academic year, there were 429,000 female students in schools, which accounted for 42.7 percent of the total student population. Additionally, there were 337,000 girls in rural areas, making up 41.7 percent of the overall student population in rural schools [Narodnoye obrazovaniye v UzSSR za 15 let: 58].

During the 1930s, there were some alterations in the structure and management of women's education. Specifically, as per the government's resolution on September 15, 1930, it became mandatory for all children to get general elementary education. According to the information, beginning in the academic year of 1930/31, children who were eight years old began attending school. The implementation of mandatory seven-year education in 1935 resulted in a certain degree of success in enticing girls to enroll in public schools. Since the inception of the Soviet Union, Soviet officials have been dedicated to promoting the empowerment and equality of women. The concept revolved around the notion of liberty and ensuring equal representation of women throughout all aspects of the economy, society, and politics in the Soviet nations [Saima Ibrahim:48]. The Soviet authorities regarded education as a crucial element of political and economic mobilization. Literacy courses, known as Likbez, were conducted in various locations such as railway carriages, tents, factories, and other available spaces. During the 1930s, it was mandatory for both boys and girls to attend primary education. Significant emphasis was placed on eradicating illiteracy specifically among women. Several cities have built specialized educational institutions exclusively for women. Subsequently, women commenced their entry into various professions, with a special focus on law, medicine, teaching, and research [Ajay Patnaik: 23–24].

The Soviet leadership viewed schools as not only institutions for imparting a comprehensive education, but also as a means of indoctrinating the younger generation with the principles and objectives of communism. The significance of women's role in society was also essential in this process. The Council of People's Commissars of the Turkestan ASSR made a decision on November 11, 1924. According to this decision, women who completed schools for the eradication of illiteracy and farmers who completed six-month courses were granted preferential loans and privileges from agricultural banks. As a condition for receiving these advantages, agricultural implements and land were assigned, and the recipients were required to make payments over a two-year period [D.Akramov: 20].

Although efforts were made in the initial years, there were numerous challenges encountered in integrating women into the Soviet education system during this period. The Presidium of the Central Executive Committee of the Uzbek SSR observed that women's

education lags far behind overall growth, based on an analysis of the initial years of incorporating women in the area of education. Simultaneously, the network of women's clubs is limited in size, insufficient funds are allocated for the upkeep of political and educational institutions, there is a shortage of female workers from the primary ethnic groups, there is a delay in providing literature and instructional materials to women's clubs and centers, and there is a noticeable deficiency in efforts to eliminate illiteracy among women of local ethnic groups. The Presidium of the Central Executive Committee of the Uzbek SSR has established a set of initiatives to promote the advancement of women's education [NAU: f. 94]:

- In order to ensure the smooth implementation of universal education in Uzbekistan, it is crucial to allocate sufficient funds in the budget plans of the People's Commissariat of Education. Specifically, it is necessary to increase the percentage of girls studying by the end of the fifth year to match the percentage of boys. This will prevent any hindrance to the introduction of universal education. Examining the presence of religious and cultural beliefs that prohibit teenagers from studying together, it is necessary to address the matter of establishing segregated girls' schools in older cities and villages. Furthermore, it is important to establish specialized schools for young female peasants interested in agriculture and crafts, while also recognizing the importance of promoting women's participation in the workforce consider the lack of pedagogic personnel in women's schools and educational institutions and the slow level of their development, strive to make reasonable and full use of the funds allocated for the repair of schools, and continue successful work on improving the qualifications of female teachers; developing the issue of expanding the network of women's corners and women's clubs; it should be envisaged to take measures to improve the organization of teaching and educational work with students in the direction of activating students in the issues of women's freedom and international education. The government's implementation of various initiatives has effectively addressed certain challenges in during women to the field of education. Nevertheless, numerous unresolved issues persisted in the sector.

In the 1920s and 1930s, various initiatives were undertaken to provide widespread access to women's education. Specifically, educational institutions dedicated to women, courses aimed at eliminating illiteracy, and institutes offering short teaching programs have undertaken extensive efforts.

Women have made a substantial contribution to the advancement of secondary and higher education. Within a brief timeframe, Uzbek women have started to rise as prominent authorities, scholars, and statespeople, joining men in actively engaging in the socio-economic and political aspects of society.

REFERENCES

1. Normurodova G. Contribution of Mahmudhodja Behbudi and its Samarkand followers to the development of the national education // International conference: Mahmudkhodja Behbudiy and press of jadids.–P. 122–127. <https://www.academia.edu/105790749/>
2. Paolo Sartori. Ijtihad in Bukhara: Central Asian Jadidism and Local Genealogies of Cultural Change // Jesho (Journal of the Economic and Social History of the Orient), 59 (2016).–P. 200–201. <https://www.academia.edu/22175126/>
3. Adeeb Khalid. Making Uzbekistan: Uzbekistan Nation, Empire, and Revolution in the Early USSR. Cornell University Press Ithaca and London, 2015.–Pp.199–200. <https://www.academia.edu/30930781/>
4. Akramov D. The role of women in the education of Uzbekistan during the Soviet rule //

- Utmishga nazar, 2022.–№4.–Pp. 19–20.
5. Sevket Hylton Akyildiz. Aims, Goals and Implementation of Soviet Education in Central Asia // The Eurasia Studies Society Journal.–Vol.1. No.1. Autumn 2012. –P. 8. <https://www.academia.edu/74573612/>
 6. Uzbekiston tarixi (1917-1991 yillar). Birinchi kitob: 1917–1936 yillar. – Toshkent: Uzbekistan, 2019.–P. 337.
 7. J.Khasanbaev. Stanovlenie i razvitie obshchego obrazovaniya vzroslykh v sovetskom Uzbekistane.–Tashkent. 1986.–P. 47.
 8. Nishonboyeva K, Cultural aspects of solving the women's issue in Uzbekistan/20-30 years. Experience and consequences. Ph.D. diss (Tashkent: Institute of History of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan, 1998)–P. 101.
 9. Narodnoye obrazovaniye v UzSSR za 15 let (1924–1939). Tashkent: Gosudarstvennoye uchebno-pedagogicheskoye izdatelstvo Uz SSR, 1939. P.58.
 10. Saima Ibrahim, Status of Women in Uzbekistan, IOSR Journal Of Humanities And Social Science (IOSR-JHSS).Volume 10, Issue 3 (Mar.–Apr. 2013).–P. 48. ISSN: 2279-0837, <https://www.academia.edu/71284491>
 11. Ajay Patnaik. Perestroika and Women Labour Force in Soviet Central Asia.–New Literature, New Delhi, January, 1989, pp.23-24.
 12. Akramov D., The role of women in the education of Uzbekistan during the period of Soviet rule, Utmishga nazar.–Volume 4. 2022 ISSN 2181-9599.–P. 20.
 13. NAU, f. 94, list 5, case 495,–Pp. from 344 to 352.